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STUDIES OF PERFORMATIVITY IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the linguistic status of performativity, which studies the formation of linguistic elements in communication. In modern linguistics, the field that studies such constructions as the performative verb, performative speech and performative text has received its place under the name «performative linguistics». Scientific work on the topic was carried out mainly by English, German, French and Russian scientists. Therefore, in our work, for the first time, we want to highlight the formation of performativity on the material of the Uzbek language. In linguistics, it is emphasized that the performative verb is used in the 1st person singular and forms sentences according to the formula **I x**. However, we believe that performativity, based only on this formula, limits its object of study. We present our scientific views on this in this article.

Key words: performativity, performance, applicative semion, episemion, performer, performand.

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TILSHUNOSLIKDA PERFORMATIVLIKNING O‘RGANILISHI HOLATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada til elementlarining muloqotda shakllanishini o‘rganuvchi performativlikning lingvistik maqomi xususida so‘z boradi. Bugungi tilshunoslikda performativ fe‘l, performativ nutq, performativ matn kabi qurilmalarni tekshiruvchi soha «performativ tilshunoslik» nomi bilan o‘z mavqeyiga ega bo‘ldi. Performatsiya xususidagi ilmiy ishlar, asosan, ingliz, nemis, fransuz, rus olimlari tomonidan amalga oshirildi. Shu bois ishimizda performativ qurilmalarning shakllanishini ilk bor o‘zbek tili materiali asosida yoritib bermoqchimiz. Lingvistikada performativ fe‘lning I shaxs birlikda, aniqlik maylida qo‘llanishi hamda Men x formulasi asosidagi jummalarni shakllantirishi ta’kidlanadi. Ammo biz performativlikning faqat shu formulaga tayangan holda ish ko‘rishini uning o‘rganish obyektini cheklab qo‘yadi deb o‘ylaymiz. Bu haqdagi ilmiy mulohazalarimizni mazkur maqolada bayon etmoqdamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: performativlik, performatsiya, applitsit semion, episemion, performer, performand.

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Факультет иностранного языка и литературы
behzodsamdchti@gmail.com**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПЕРФОРМАТИВНОСТИ В ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье рассматривается лингвистический статус перформативности, изучающей формирование языковых элементов в общении. В современной лингвистике область, изучающая такие конструкции, как перформативный глагол, перформативная речь и перформативный текст, получила свое место под названием «перформативная лингвистика». Научную работу над темой вели в основном английские, немецкие, французские и русские ученые. Поэтому в своей работе мы хотим впервые осветить формирование перформативности на материале узбекского языка. В языкознании подчеркивается, что перформативный глагол употребляется в 1-м лице единственного числа и образует предложения по формуле Я х. Однако мы считаем, что перформативность, основанная только на этой формуле, ограничивает ее объект исследования. Мы представляем наши научные взгляды на это в этой статье.

Ключевые слова: перформо, перформация, апплицитный семион, эписемион, перформатор, перформанд.

While the field of linguistics is progressing along the world sciences, performative linguistics is also establishing a research center like its other types of prospects such as descriptive, generative and cognitive linguistics. Performative linguistics enriches the process of describing the language and modeling its components. In this aspect, it differs from structural linguistics, which studies the structure of language. In other words, performative linguistics studies the formation of language elements in communication. For example, if we were pay attention to the meaning expressed by the suffix **-a**, we would have to take into account not only the words being formed, but also the possibilities of the existing affix: jazz+**a** (noun); ko'tar+**a** (adjective); bur+**a** (verb); sen-**a** (particles); there is no availability to make an adverb, though it can be done in words which comes in its function: yur+**a**-yur+**a** (gerund). Accordingly, considering all possibilities of linguistic elements in language system, performative linguistics serves to enrich the system with new structures. Besides, it determines the role and function of these structures that can be used practically in speech. As the result, the word or grammatical form as a language element finds its place in language and speech. In this respect, it is close to derivational linguistics and pragmatology.

It is important to mention that we interpret performativity from the point of view of linguistic science. In fact, performativity is closely related to a number of disciplines such as anthropology, social and cultural geography, economics, gender studies, jurisprudence, history, philosophy, taking into account that language can function as a form of social action.

The term «performo» comes from Latin and means «to create», «to compose», «to operate». D.Yum explained scientific views about performativity in philosophy[1]. In linguistics, we observe the comments about it in the studies of E.Benvenist and N.D.Arutyunova[2].

By the 60s and 70s, linguistic pragmatics emerged as one of the unique directions as a field that studies the communication process. Philosophy of language served as the main source for the development of linguistic pragmatics. The merits of P.F.Strawson, G.P.Grays, J.L.Austin, J.R.Sears were great in creating the theory of communicative acts[3]. J.Austin, commenting on discourse, emphasizes the existence of performative and constative types of thought expression[4.22-129]. In this way notions like performative verb, performative speech, performative text, are began to be widely studied in linguistics. And nowadays, the field that check such devices got its position in linguistics under the name of «performative linguistics». As the result, many works of foreign linguists devoted to the interpretation of this issue were presented to the scientific community. In

existing works, semantic and pragmatic features of performativity, specific types of performativity, issues such as the importance of the tools, which create it, have been widely disclosed. Such works, especially, were mainly carried out by English, German, French and Russian scientist. We can include linguists such as D. Leach, D. Versuren, K. Bach, R. Harnish, T. Ballmer, B. Brennenshul, A. Vejbitskaya, Y. Krasina, V. Ponomarenko, N. Lerfilyeva, I. Kobozeva, Y. Apresyan, S. Chastnikova, I. Shatunovsky, G. Pochevsov. In Turkic studies, it is known that there is work by Azerbaijani professor R. K. Rasulov entitled «Performative speaking genre of sacred discourse in the Turkic epic «Kitabi-dede Korkut»». Also, we see that in Uzbek linguistics, although not specially devoted to the interpretation of performative devices, there are scientific views expressed about this concept.

Taking into account the above points, for the first time, in this work we are going to express formation of performative devices based on the material of the Uzbek language. First of all, we have to dwell on the classification of performative meaning expression:

- 1) approval and special appeals (to inform, to announce, to remind, to deny, to confirm, to emphasize, to testify, to convince, to entrust);
- 2) confession (self-blame, to repent, to admit);
- 3) promise (to guarantee, to swear an oath, give an assurance);
- 4) request (to plead, to beg, entreat);
- 5) suggestion and advice (give an advice, offer, to recommend);
- 6) to warn (to predict, give a warning);
- 7) request and command (to command, make a condition, to demand);
- 8) prohibition and permission (to allow, to forbid, announcing sanction, to deprive);
- 9) consent and objection (to deny, to agree, argue, to rebel);
- 10) approval (to praise, to approve, to bless, to express inclination);
- 11) judgement (to punish, to curse, to blame, to censure, to fine);
- 12) excuse (forgive, absolve).

Generally, in addition to those listed, there are many other types of social communication that express performativity. Consequently, the speech process, a person creates devices that express these meanings according to the situation, by the way, taking into account all possibilities of linguistic elements in language system, the system will be enriched with new structures.

As we mentioned previously, there are performative and constative types of thought expression. If constatives only describe and report reality, performatives express situations that can lead to certain consequences for both the speaker and the listener. For proof of concept, we turn to the following example:

–Ma, bolam, o‘ynab kel, barvaqt qayt. Baqqolning maymunidek kim ko‘ringanda ajuva bo‘lib yurma, pochta chining otidek har bir do‘konning oldida to‘xtab, ag‘rayma, qassoblikka kirib qolgan begona itdek ko‘ringan bilan yoqalashma. Hayitda qandolat bozoriga tushgan qishloqidek badnafs bo‘lma, ko‘ringan narsani olib yeya berma. Ha, shunday bo‘lsin, bolam, shunday bo‘lsin (G‘.G‘ulom. Shum bola).

(-Take a walk, son, just come back early. And do not grimace, don't be a laughingstock to everyone you meet, like a grocer's monkey: don't yawn at every shop like a mail horse, and don't get into a fight with any idler, like a stray dog in a butcher's market and don't overeat, look like a yokel simpleton, who during a Eid, entered in a shopping mall...do not taste everything that you see, so that's it, son, yes (G. Gulom «The Rascal»)).

The given example is fully performative speech, in which, as an expression of advice, it is stated in order to eliminate the possibility of some consequences. This situation, in turn, shows that performativity is related to causative linguistics. Because, causative linguistics studies the cause and effect relationships[6]. Besides, the basic structures of the simple sentences that make up the general structure of this text are morphologically expressed through the second person of the imperative. On the one hand, it gives the meaning of encouragement, and on the other hand, it reveals the expression of advice. Due to the fact that causativeness is related to the meaning of encouragement, this text is formed on the basis of the law of performative causation. If the formation is determined, then the derivation is also present. Therefore, we consider this device to be the result of perfocause derivation.

It is worth to note that it should not be understood that the basic structures of the sentence will not always performative, if they expressed morphologically in second person of the imperative. After all, the meaning of threatening I also reflected in such form. The content of bullying or insults is not perceived as performative. They belong to the pure causative. However, forms in the text such as come back early, don't yawn, don't get into a fight can also come in the meaning of threatening. Nevertheless, we consider these words to be performative verbs based on the general content of the text. The fact is that the linguistic signs in the text, in concretizing their content, are syntactically connected with other language signs and enter into special derivative relations with them that are characteristics of this text. In other words, one of the recognized meanings of the word will be updated, for example, a word completely changes its meaning under the influence of context (undefined context synonyms will appear in dictionary). This brings out performative. For example, let's pay attention to the meaning of words like 'monkey', 'horse', 'dog', 'yokel' in compounds grocer's monkey, mail horse, stray dog in a butcher's market, yokel simpleton, who during an Eid, entered in a shopping mall. The concept of exiting words can be different for various people in different situation. For zoologist monkey is an animal who live in a forest and a jungle, actor for handler of monkeys in the circus, for someone a person who was a laughing stock. Just like this for butcher horse is a meat, for traveler as a transportation, competitor in the competition of horses, determines the type of army in the military and so on. However, these words in the text that we are analyzing, they service to acquire the meaning of admonition related to the classification of performative. It is true that they do not give performative when they taken separately, but in their presence, the meaning of simile emerges: as do not be like a horse, monkey, and a dog. The system of the language is enriched with new structures. Of course, verbs and auxiliary verb phrases like take a walk, come back earlier, don't be laughingstock to everyone you meet, do not grimace, don't get into a fight, do not eat perfokausa acts as a performer in the derivation. In other words, language elements complement each other and create a performative text.

It should be said that the performative text is based on the applicative model of derivation. For example, the sentence Ma, bolam, o'ynab kel, barvaqt qayt (here, son, take a walk, come back early) is made up of applicative semiotics of phoneme combinations, which requires nine steps: 1) Ma; 2) bola; 3) -m; 4) o'yin; 5) -a; 6) -b; 7) kel; 8) barvaqt; 9) qayt (1) here; 2) son; 3) affix; 4) game; 5) affix; 6) affix; 7) come; 8) back; 9) early). So, the logical sequence of phonemes ensures the creation of a word. This is the generation of the language signs. To be exact, in this process we observe the formation of language and speech units. This space is called a generator space. About generator space B.N.Turniyazov makes the following statement: «In generator space language units works on the basis of the connector. in this case, the initial module (the first formed form) is the basis, and applicative semions (an element composed of semiotic signs and having a certain meaning) are created from it, and from this are formed episemions. Extender of applicative semions is called relator (an element that rests on some base). This situation can be imagined as a geometric progression. In every stage of derivation, the next semion is a relator, representing a broader episemion than the previous one. So, every relying element regardless of whether it is a phoneme or morpheme, comes as a relator»[6.150-151].

In this way we observe the expansion of episemions from applicative semions:

Ma, bolam, o'ynab kel, barvaqt qayt (here, son, take a walk, come back early) – the first applicative episemion; performer: **o'ynab kel, barvaqt qayt (take a walk, come back early)**;

Baqqolning maymunidek kim ko'ringanda ajuva bo'lib yurma (don't be a laughingstock to everyone you meet, like a grocer's monkey) – the second applicative episemion; performer: **ajuva bo'lib yurma (don't be a laughingstock)**;

pochtachining otidek har bir do'konning oldida to'xtab, ag'rayma (don't yawn at every shop like a mail horse) – the third applicative episemion; performer: **ag'rayma (don't yawn)**;

qassoblikka kirib qolgan begona itdek ko'ringan bilan yoqalashma (don't get into a fight with any idler, like a stray dog in a butcher's market) – the fourth applicative episemion; performer: **yoqalashma (don't get into a fight)**;

Hayitda qandolat bozoriga tushgan qishloqidek badnafs bo'lma, ko'ringan narsani olib yeya berma (don't overeat, look like a yokel simpleton, who during a Eid, entered in a shopping mall... do not taste everything that you see) – the fifth applicative episemion; performato: **badnafs bo'lma, yeya berma (don't overeat, look like a yokel simpleton, do not taste everything that you see);**

Ha, shunday bo'lsin, bolam, shunday bo'lsin (so that's it, son, yes) – the sixth applicative episemion; performato: **shunday bo'lsin (so that's it).**

As we can see, episemions formed from applicit semions require a six-stage performative derivation. Each language element that creates a performative situation is a performant. Although these elements are considered operands in derivation, they are also called performants because they represent a performative device. In other words, they do not leave operand function as a language material, but the performative device is expressed through these elements. It should be noted that basic structures of performative devices that coming in the status of episemions, up to the sixth stage they mean the meaning of advice of performance. However, after reaching the sixth stage, they represent the affirmative meaning of performance. In this, of course, performative verbs are of a great importance, because the types of meaning of performance are understood through verbs. Therefore, we can see that there are different meanings of performance the same device in a macro performative situation.

It is important to notice that in linguistic, the performative verb is used in the 1st person singular, for indicative mood and the view that from the devices based on formula **I x**, for example, I declare the meeting open, I advise, I announce the sanction, is the leading view [7.electronic resource]. We can agree with this opinion, but the meaning of performative advice is not always based on this formula. Compare: Baqqolning maymunidek kim ko'ringanda ajuva bo'lib yurma (don't be a laughingstock to everyone you meet, like a grocer's monkey) – Baqqolning maymunidek kim ko'ringanda ajuva bo'lib yurmamaslikni nasihat qilaman (I exhort you to do not be a laughingstock to everyone you meet, like a grocer's monkey).

The second of the compared sentences does not correspond very well to the stylistic rules of Uzbek language. In this case, it is more correct to use the combination I advice like: Baqqolning maymunidek kim ko'ringanda ajuva bo'lib yurmamaslikni maslahat beraman (I advice you to do not be a laughingstock to everyone you meet, like a grocer's monkey). However, the meanings of exhort and advice are very different from each other. For this reason, we think that it would be appropriate to analyze performativity based on the characteristics of a particular language. Therefore, we can easily say that our analyzed example is related to the performativity that explains the meaning of exhort. Except from this, the sentence Ha, shunday bo'lsin, bolam, shunday bo'lsin (so that's it, son, yes) is emphasizing and exaggerating that the thoughts coming before it are related to exhort like: Men shuni nasihat qilyapman (I'm exhorting this).

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МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

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